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**Does pilocarpine hydrochloride modulate
neutrophil chemotactic chemokine
expression by oral mucosa in response to
Candida albicans infections?**

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Abbreviations

ANOVA:	Analysis of variance
BPE:	Bovine pituitary extract
BSA:	Bovine serum albumin
cDNA:	Complementary deoxyribonucleic acid
COPD:	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
dNTP:	Deoxynucleoside triphosphate mixture (A,T,G,C)
DMEM:	Dulbecco's modified Eagles medium
DMSO:	Dimethyl sulphoxide
DPBS:	Dulbecco's phosphate buffered saline
EDTA:	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
EGF:	Epidermal growth factor
ELISA:	Enzyme linked immunosorbent assay
FBS:	Foetal Bovine Serum
GAPDH:	Glyceraldehydes-3-phosphahet dehydrogenase
G-CSF:	Granulocytes colony stimulating factor-3
IL:	Interleukin
IU:	International units
KSFM:	Keratinocytes serum-free medium
mg:	milligram
mL:	milliliter
mRNA:	Messenger ribonucleic acid
PBS:	Phosphate buffered saline
PCR:	Polymerase chain reaction
PHCL:	Pilocarpine hydrochloride.
RNA:	Ribonucleic acid
RT-PCR:	Real-time Polymerase chain reaction
RPM:	Revolutions per minutes
RPMI:	RPMI 1640 medium
SAB:	Sabouraud dextrose agar
TLRs:	Toll-like receptors
TMB:	<i>3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine</i>
TNF:	Tumor necrosis factor
TWEEN®:	Polyoxyethylene sorbitan monooleate
µL:	microliter
µm:	micrometer
XTT:	2,3-Bis-(2-Methoxy-4-Nitro-5-Sulfophenyl)-2 <i>H</i> -Tetrazolium-5-Carboxanilide
YPD:	yeast peptone dextrose broth

Abstract

Oropharyngeal candidiasis is a serious clinical dilemma within the immunosuppressed and elderly population, commonly caused by *Candida albicans* species. The ability of *C. albicans* to infect the epithelial cells is mediated by the dimorphic switching to virulent hyphae form while expressing different virulence patterns to facilitates cell invasion. The cellular immune response to *Candida* infection is mediated by toll-like receptors, which signals the recruitment of neutrophils to the infection site by the release of chemokines/cytokines (IL-8/IL-6). Current research suggests that the non-neurogenic cholinergic system has an immune regulating/antibiofilm functions facilitated by muscarinic receptors found on epithelial keratinocytes and *Candida* species, respectively. This study aimed firstly to evaluate the immune modulating effect of a general muscarinic receptor agonist, pilocarpine hydrochloride (PHCL) against *C. albicans* infection, using TR146 cell lines as an *in vitro* model of oral epithelium. Secondly, to determine the antibiofilm/antimetabolic effect of PHCL on 22 clinical *Candida* isolates.

Three concentrations of PHCL (1 mM, 5 mM, and 25 mM) with/without *C. albicans* (SC5315) were used to treat monolayers of epithelial cells (TR146) in two-time intervals (4h and 24h). Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay and real-time PCR were used to determine the effect of *C. albicans* and PHCL on expression of Interleukin-6 and interleukin-8 by TR146 epithelial cells. The antibiofilm and antimetabolic effects of 25 mM PHCL on 22 clinical *Candida* isolates after 24 h were determined using crystal violet and XTT assays, respectively.

A dose-dependent inhibition of IL-6 and IL-8 expression occurred in cells stimulated with *C. albicans* and PHCL. PHCL at 25 mM induced a significant reduction in the

biofilm biomass of most of the clinical *Candida* isolates after treatment, while induced a significant metabolic inhibitory effect against high biofilm forming isolates only compared to control.

In conclusion, PHCL represents a promising therapeutic alternative to conventional antifungals. However, further studies should consider the role of each muscarinic receptor for a more selective antifungal effect.

Introduction

Oral fungal infections are one of the most common pathologies that dentists may come across throughout their career. These infections can be a significant source of morbidity, pain, discomfort, debilitation, and even death (Cheng et al., 2005),(Kali et al., 2013). The anatomic location of the oral cavity and the rich blood supply of the head and neck could impose an additional risk for the dissemination of these infections, especially in high-risk individuals (Tang et al., 2014). In the USA, blood stream infections by *Candida* species have been ranked as the fourth most common among other organisms, particularly in procedures that depend on intravascular lines (Wenzel et al., 2004).

Candida is a dimorphic fungus and an opportunistic pathogen, which is commonly found along with the commensal normal flora of the skin and mucosal membranes. More than 200 species are included in the genus *Candida*, most of them are not pathogenic to human (Dignani et al., 2009). In healthy individuals, *Candida* species have been found to be present in 25% to 75% of the population without causing any pathologies (Cannon et al., 1995), (Odds, 1988). *Candida albicans* is one of the most common candida species isolated from over 80% of oral lesions (Reichart et al., 2000). The dimorphism of *C. albicans* and its ability to switch between yeast and hypha forms is considered problematic during treatment and diagnosis. Moreover, other virulence factors that may complicate the eradication of oral *C. albicans* are its ability to resist antifungals by the formation of a biofilm, increase in expression of adhesins, phenotypic switching, release of hydrolytic enzymes, alternation in

metabolic processes and fungal cell wall mechanical properties (Noble et al., 2010), (Calderone and Fonzi, 2001), (Bliss et al., 2012), (Sun et al., 2010).

Different local and systemic predisposing factors have been found to alter the host protective elements or create a favourable local environment for the growth of *Candida*. For instance, patients with Sjogren syndrome, who lack enough salivary protective secretions, are more susceptible to oral fungal infections (Peluso et al., 2007) ,(Sherman et al., 2002). In addition, geriatric patients with denture appliances have an increased susceptibility to fungal infections, as *Candida* species remain protected from the salivary cleansing effect under the fitting surface of the prosthesis, which acts as an effective reservoir for microorganisms (Garg et al., 2012). Research has also found that patients undergoing pharmacological therapy, including broad-spectrum antibiotics, xerogenic, and immune suppressant drugs may become more prone to oral candidiasis (Farah et al., 2000), (Ellepola and Samaranayake, 2001), (Sherman et al., 2002). Moreover, endocrine disorders (diabetes, hypothyroidism, and hypoparathyroidism), extremes in age, radiotherapy/chemotherapy, blood dyscrasias, and HIV are also factors increasing the likelihood of fungal infections (Darwazeh and Darwazeh, 2014).

The human oral epithelium is not only a protective barrier

The oral epithelium is considered the first line of defence against oral pathogens. oral epithelial cells act not only as a protective barrier against the invasion of oral microorganisms and exogenous peptides but also control the anti-microbial immune response after the detection of pathogenic molecular patterns of microorganisms by specific receptors. These receptors are mostly Toll-like and C-type lectin receptors, which are expressed on the surface of epithelial cells, including keratinocyte and

fibroblasts. Along with the ability of keratinocytes to recognize *Candida* infections, they act as immunocytes by producing antimicrobial peptides such as β defensin and cathelicidins and stimulating the release of cytokines, chemokines, and arachidonic acid metabolites (Janik and Heffernan, 2008), (de Repentigny et al., 2004).

Studies have suggested that *C. albicans* must overcome several challenges before establishing an infection. These include competing with commensal oral flora, tolerating hostile environmental circumstances (temperature, moisture, and PH), and resisting antifungals secreted by keratinocytes and early cellular immune responses (Feller et al., 2014). The phenotypic switching of *C. albicans* to its hyphal form and the expression of surface adhesions enables it to bind to the surface of oral epithelial keratinocytes (Zhu and Filler, 2010). The penetration of *C. albicans* through and in between keratinocytes is achieved by the release of hydrolytic enzymes such as proteinases, lipases, and mucolytic enzymes at the advancing tips of hyphae (Zhu and Filler, 2010). This process has been suggested to occur in a faster than the rate of keratinocytes shedding, otherwise, *C. albicans* would be eliminated (Feller et al., 2014), (Verma, 2008).

After the initial invasion of *C. albicans* through the superficial layer of the epithelium, the depth of invasion may not be that enough to elicit clinically detectable inflammation (Wächtler et al., 2011). Research has reported that the severity of inflammation depends on the depth of invasion, the extent of the damaged epithelium, and expression of additional virulence factors (Villar et al., 2007). For instance, a high incidence of life-threatening invasive infections has been reported, especially in patients enduring invasive clinical procedures or experiencing major trauma. These may act as factors for *the* dissemination of *Candida* infections through bloodstream leading to high chances of mortality (Brown et al., 2012).

The epithelial immune response against *Candida*

The dimorphic switching of *C. albicans* from a yeast to hyphae form involve a change in polysaccharide capsule and cell wall structure, which lead to expression of different pathogenic patterns. Upon the activation of these pathogenic molecular pattern by *Candida*, an immune inflammatory response, through intracellular signalling pathway, begins as a result of interaction with germline-encoded pattern recognition receptors of the innate immune cells and keratinocytes (Cassel et al., 2009), (Gringhuis et al., 2011). Consequently, different cytokines and chemokines are released from the keratinocytes such as IL-1 α / β , IL-6, and IL-8, which recruit, activate, and differentiate immune cells (Steele and Fidel, 2002).

It has been reported that oral epithelial cells respond to the damage caused by *C. albicans* invasion through the release of IL- α , which acts as a chemokine for boosting inflammatory response, including the release of host defence peptides (Verma et al., 2017). Host defence peptides such as β -defensin family and cathelicidin, have been found to exhibit broad spectrum activity by targeting the cell wall/membrane of microorganisms resulting in the formation of pores that lead to cytoplasmic membrane dysfunction and ATP/ion release (Guilhelmelli et al., 2013). Nevertheless, research has suggested that some host defence peptides may also help in modulating cytokines and chemokines release (Hemshkhar et al., 2016). For instance, cathelicidins, LL-37, and CRAMP have been found to promote immunity by the recruitment and activation of innate immune cells such as neutrophils.

Innate immune response and fungal infection

Neutrophils are the most abundant types of granulocytes and form an essential part of the innate immune system that is responsible in controlling and eliminating microbial infections. The capacity of neutrophils to destroy the invading fungus is accomplished by both intracellular and extracellular mechanisms. For instance, neutrophils can kill the phagocytosed fungi intracellularly by the release reactive oxidative metabolites and granule products. Nevertheless, neutrophils can also eliminate fungal invasion by the release of extracellular antimicrobial proteins at the site of infections (Bellocchio et al., 2004), (Urban et al., 2009).

IL-1 facilitates the initial recruitment of neutrophils by stimulating the release of granulocyte stimulating factor G-CSF, a key trigger for emergency granulopoiesis (Altmeier et al., 2016). The attracted neutrophils at the site of inflammation have the capacity to not only kill fungi but also indirectly upregulate the expression Toll-like receptor (TRL4) on the oral keratinocytes. This is achieved by several cytokines including TNF in a process that does not require neutrophil infiltration of mucosal tissue(Weindl et al., 2010). The peptides released by neutrophils (human neutrophils peptides) can also facilitate the secretion of IL-8 by epithelial cells, to attract more leukocytes (Syeda et al., 2008). In addition, some other host defence peptides have been found to stimulate the production of CxC1, IL-8/CXC8, CXC2, CXC4, CXC20, and RANTES at physiologic concentrations (Mookherjee et al., 2006), (Choi et al., 2012) . Several studies have suggested that this cellular crosstalk between polymorphonuclear cells and oral keratinocytes is the main mechanism of protecting against *C. albicans*- induced tissue damage (Moyes and Naglik, 2011), (Moyes and Naglik, 2011) .

On the other hand, multiple strategies appear to have been crafted in the host barrier surface such as the secretion of IL-6 to eliminate invasive *C. albicans*. An in vitro study has shown that IL-6 can act as polymorphonuclear secretagogue by stimulating lysozyme, lactoferrin and β -glucuronidase secretion, activities that reinforce the capacity of these to terminate fungal targets (Borish et al., 1989), (Palma et al., 1992). It has been reported that people with oral candidiasis have a significantly elevated IL-6 serum level compared to healthy controls (Yamamoto et al., 1994). Research has suggested that IL-6 induce a rapid protective peripheral blood neutrophilia during infection (Borish et al., 1989).

Similarly, the release of IL-8 by human keratocytes has been suggested to have a potent neutrophils chemoattractant functions (Yamamoto et al., 1994), and has the ability to promote the degranulation and antifungal activities of polymorphonuclear leukocytes (Djeu et al., 1990).

Past and present fungal therapeutic agents

Several systemic and non-systemic (topical) agents have been proposed for the treatment of oral fungal infections such as Gentian Violet, polyenes, and azoles. Before the 1950s, Gentian Violet was one of the most popular agents for the treatment of oral fungal infections (Telles et al., 2017). Although it is still being used in some underdeveloped countries due to its cost-effectiveness and availability, other countries have stopped using it, especially, after the introduction of more effective drugs such as polyenes. Other factors were due to the side effects of Gentian Violet like mucosal irritation and staining (Samaranayake and Ferguson, 1994). After the 1950s, the discovery of

polyenes, such as amphotericin B and nystatin, was a great breakthrough in the field of fungal treatment, especially in immunocompromised individuals.

These antifungals have been suggested to act on ergosterol and sterol of the cell membrane of *Candida*, altering its permeability, and resulting in the destruction of the *Candida* organism (Telles et al., 2017).

On the other hand, fungistatic drugs such as azoles have been found to affect the growth of *Candida* by interfering with the synthesis of ergosterol, causing a change in the permeability of the cell membrane (Epstein, 2003). Despite the effectiveness of some of these new antifungal agents, there is still concern about the toxicity and the increasing resistance of some fungal species against these drugs, especially in immunocompromised patients who have undergone repeated courses of antifungal therapy (M. Dixon and Walsh, 1996).

Cholinergic Agonists as a possible treatment for *Candida* infection

The reason behind the lagged development of antifungals behind that of antibacterial agents is most probably due to the cellular structure of prokaryotes, which offer numerous structural and metabolic targets that differ from the human host. In contrast, fungi cell types resemble that of human cells (Eukaryotes), which make most agents that are toxic to fungi also toxic to human (M. Dixon and Walsh, 1996). In the recent years, a great effort is being made to search for new therapeutic agents to eliminate fungal biofilms and stop virulent behaviour with fewer side effects. Several studies have highlighted the importance of the non-cholinergic pathway for modulating the cellular immune response against fungal infections, inhibition of morphogenesis,

biofilm formation, and the expression of virulence factors (Rajendran et al., 2015b), (Nile et al., 2019). Acetylcholine is a neurotransmitter synthesized by both prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells, and almost every cell in the human body including keratinocytes, fibroblasts, monocytes, macrophages, B cells, and T cells (Wessler and Kirkpatrick, 2008), (Wessler et al., 2003), (Kawashima and Fujii, 2008). Previous studies have found that acetylcholine can promote rapid clearance of *C. albicans*, while protecting against inflammatory-induced tissue damage (Bencherif et al., 2011). Being synthesized from acetyl coenzyme A and choline by the enzyme choline *acetyltransferase*, the multiple functions of acetylcholine have been attributed to its ability to act on both nicotinic and muscarinic receptors. Studies have suggested that the nicotinic receptors, particularly the $\alpha 7$ nAChR, may have an important role in immune cells differentiation, maturation, and recruitment to the infection site (Nile et al., 2019), (Thornton et al., 2011), (Koval et al., 2008). On the other hand, recent studies have shown that muscarinic receptors display multiple immune stimulatory and regulatory functions in human epithelial cells (Darby et al., 2015), (Kistemaker et al., 2013, Eglen, 2006). These receptor were also suggested to play a role modulating filamentation and biofilm formation of *C. albicans* in a *G. mellonella* infection model (Nile et al., 2019).

Pilocarpine (PHCL), a general muscarinic receptor agonist, has been widely used in dentistry to treat patients with xerostomia and decreased lacrimal gland secretions. While five muscarinic receptors (mAChR) subtypes (M1-M5) were suggested to be present in human cells, PHCL acts predominantly on M1 and M3 mAChsR (Figueroa et al., 2009). To activate secondary receptors and facilitate ion channel activities,

these receptors must be coupled to G-proteins. Several studies have demonstrated that the G-protein coupled receptors are also expressed by *C. albicans*, which promote filamentation, biofilm formation, and extracellular signal sensing (Xue et al., 2008), (Maidan et al., 2005), (Zoheir et al., 2012). Moreover, studies have shown several important roles for M1 and M5 mAChsR in human such as regulating innate immune functions and cytolytic activities (Mandelli et al., 2000).

Hypothesis

It is our hypothesis that PHCL can modulate neutrophil chemotactic chemokine expression by oral epithelial cell model in response to *C. albicans* infection, while promoting the clearance of *Candida* infection by neutralizing their virulence factors.

Aims of the study

- 1- To evaluate the immune modulatory effect of PHCL on the level of IL-6 and IL-8 protein expression by TR146 oral epithelial cell model in response to *C. albicans* infection.
- 2- To evaluate the cell damaging effect of PHCL and *C. albicans* using oral epithelial cell model.
- 3- To assess the antibiofilm and antimetabolic effects of PHCL on 22 clinical *Candida* isolates.

Methodology

TR146 culture and passage

The TR146 cell line (Cancer Research Technology, London, UK) is an epithelial cell line derived from a human neck metastasis originating from buccal mucosa (Rupniak et al., 1985). The cells were stored routinely in Microbank™ vials in liquid nitrogen until required (Glasgow Dental Hospital, UK). TR146 has been purposed as model of human buccal epithelium (Jacobsen et al., 1995).

A cryovial of TR146 oral epithelial cells in Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) solution (Initial passaging number; 8), was retrieved from liquid nitrogen, and rapidly thawed in a water bath at a 37 °C. Next, the vial was centrifuged at 13000 RPM for 10 minutes, diluted in Gibco™ Defined Keratinocyte Serum-Free media (DKSFM), and incubated in 75-cm² tissue-culture flask in 5% CO₂ at 37 °C for two days.

The adherence and the confluence of cells were checked on the third day under the microscope, followed by replacing the media with 15 mL of fresh 1:1 Gibco™ keratinocyte Serum-Free Media (KSFM) and Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM). The flask was once again incubated in 5% CO₂ at 37 °C to reach a confluence of 70 to 80%. All solutions were prepared as shown in Table 1.

The TR146 cells were grown in 75-cm² tissue culture flask as described above. For passage, 5 mL of 0.5% Trypsin/EDTA solution was added into the 75-cm² flask to cover the adherent monolayer surface and the flask was incubated in 5% CO₂ at 37 °C for 15 min. As soon as the cells were detached, 15 mL of DMEM was added into the

flask and then the cells were pelleted by centrifugation at 13,000 RPM. Finally, the cell pellet was resuspended in 10 mL KSFM and live cell counting using trypan blue solution (0.4%) (Sigma-Aldrich, UK) was performed under the light microscope using a Neubauer hemocytometer (Fisher Scientific, UK), followed by standardization to 2×10^5 cells/mL before seeding into 24-well culture plates and incubated overnight in 5% CO₂ at 37 °C.

Culture Media	Supplements					
DKSFM	Bovine Pituitary Extract (BPE) is replaced with defined growth promoting additives (Insulin, Epidermal Growth Factors (EGF) and Fibroblast Growth Factors) – concentrations not given.					
KSFM	100 IU Penicillin	100 µg Streptomycin	25 µg/mL BPE	0.2 ng/mL EGF	0.3 CaCl ₂ (0.4 mM total Ca ²⁺)	
DMEM	100 IU Penicillin	100 µg Streptomycin	25 µg/mL BPE	0.2 ng/mL EGF	10% Foetal bovine Serum (FBS)	0.3 CaCl ₂ (0.4 mM total Ca ²⁺)
	Note: Filter/sterilisation of BPE and EGF was done through 0.2 µm filter pore.					

Table 1: Solutions were supplemented as per the instruction provided by manufacturer (Gibco™, Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Culture and standardisation of *Candida albicans*

Candida albicans laboratory strain SC5314 was cultured on a Sabouraud's dextrose agar [(SAB) (Sigma-Aldrich, Dorset, UK)] plate and incubated at 30 °C for 48 h. A broth was then prepared by inoculating yeast peptone dextrose [(YPD) (Sigma-Aldrich, Dorset, UK)] media (1% yeast extract, 2% peptone, 2% dextrose) with yeast cell colonies using a plastic disposable loop and incubating overnight at 30 °C at 200 RPM, in an orbital shaker (IKA KS 4000 i control, Berlin, Germany). The following day, *C. albicans* yeast cells were centrifuged at 3000 RPM for 10 minutes, washed two times in 10 mL phosphate buffered saline (1X PBS), and then diluted 1:100 in PBS to enable enumeration of cells/mL under the microscope using a Neubauer haemocytometer (Fisher Scientific, UK). For stimulation experiments, *C. albicans* was standardised to a concentration of 4×10^4 cell/mL in KSFM media.

Culture and standardization of clinical *Candida* isolates

Clinical *Candida* isolates used in these investigations were recovered from two previous studies on denture induced stomatitis conducted at Glasgow dental hospital, Glasgow, UK, Table 2. These isolates were stored routinely in Microbank™ vials (Prolab diagnostics, UK) at -80 °C until required. Briefly, Isolates were initially grown on SAB (Sigma-Aldrich, Dorset, UK) plates at 30 °C for 48h. A loopful of cells from SAB plates of each *Candida* isolates were inoculated into 10 mL of YPD (Sigma-Aldrich, Dorset, UK) media and incubated overnight, on an orbital shaker (IKA KS 4000 i control, Berlin, Germany) at 200 RPM at 30 °C. The following day, the cells were centrifuged at 3000 RPM for 10 minutes, and the pellets were

resuspended in 10 mL PBS. The cell suspensions were then diluted 1:100 and cells were numerated as described above. All isolates were standardized to a concentration of 2×10^6 cells/mL in RPMI medium.

	Low Biofilm Forming						High Biofilm Forming						Source
Clinical Candida Isolates	GSK 031	GSK 053	GSK 065	GSK 072	GSK 113	GSK 123	GSK 004	GSK 010	GSK 025	GSK 061	GSK 090	GSK 093	Denture stomatitis (O'Donnell et al., 2017)
	BC 023	BC 037	BC 038	BC 039	BC 044		BC 020	BC 117	BC 136	BC 145	BC 146		Denture stomatitis (Coco et al., 2008)

Table 2: Clinical Candida isolates were previously characterized based on the biofilm forming ability.

Biofilm biomass and metabolic activity assays

To determine effect of PHCL on the 22 clinical *Candida* isolates, 100 μL of standardised cell suspension of each oral *Candida* isolate were transferred to 8 wells (4 positive controls and 4 treatment groups) of a sterilized flat-bottomed, 96-well plate (Costar, Corning Incorporated, NY, USA). For the treatment groups, 100 μL of 50 mM of PHCL in RPMI medium was pipetted into each of the treatment wells to reach a final drug and yeast cell concentrations of 25 mM and 1×10^6 cell/mL, respectively. One hundred microliter of RPMI media only was pipetted into each of the control wells. This obtained a final yeast cell concentration of 1×10^6 cells/mL. The plates were then incubated for 24 hours at 30 °C and XTT/crystal violet assays were performed the following day to determine the effect of PHCL on biofilm formation and metabolic activity, respectively.

2,3-Bis-(2-Methoxy-4-Nitro-5-Sulfophenyl)-2H-Tetrazolium-5-Carboxanilide (XTT) Reduction Assay

The effect of 25 mM PHCL on the metabolic activity of 22 clinical *Candida* isolates after 24h was assessed using the XTT-reduction assay, adapted from previous studies (Pierce et al., 2008). Briefly, XTT (Sigma-Aldrich, UK) saturated solution of 0.5 g/L was prepared in PBS. The solution was then filter/sterilised through 0.22 μm filter, aliquoted and used immediately or stored at -80 °C for later use.

The media in each well of the 96-well plate was removed from the cells by careful pipetting and the adherent cells were washed with 100 μL of PBS. One hundred

microliter of XTT-menadione solution was pipetted into each of the wells, and the plate was incubated in the dark for 2 hours at 37 °C. Seventy-five microliter of the reaction solution was transferred to a new flat-bottomed 96-well plate and the original left to dry overnight for later biofilm biomass quantification (Crystal violet Assay). Finally, the absorbance was measured at 492 nm using a FluoStar Omega (BMG LABTECH, UK) microplate reader. Data for each well was blank corrected and presented as OD absorbance values [The colour change in the XTT reduction assay is directly related to the metabolic activity of the biofilm as previously described (Ramage et al., 2001)].

Biofilm biomass quantification

Biofilm biomass was quantified using crystal violet solution on the dried adherent biofilm. One hundred microliter of 0.05% of crystal violet solution was pipetted into each well and the plate incubated at room temperature for 20 min. Afterwards, the media was discarded, and the biofilms were washed carefully under running water to remove excess stain and then blotted to dry. Finally, 100 µL of 100% ethanol was pipetted into each well to solubilize the crystal violet for 1 minute, followed by transferring 75 µL of the ethanol into a new 96-well plate. The absorbance was then measured at 570 nm using microplate reader (FluoStar Omega, BMG LABTECH, UK). Data of each well was blank corrected and presented as OD absorbance values [The absorbance is proportional to the quantity of biofilm mass, the greater the biofilm, the higher the staining and absorbance (Mowat et al., 2007)].

Stimulation experiments

One millilitre of TR146 cell suspension with a density of 2×10^5 cells/mL was pipetted into each well of a 24-well culture plates (Costar, Corning Incorporated, NY, USA) and incubated overnight in 5% CO₂ at 37 °C. Monolayers of TR146 cells were then infected in duplicate with 2×10^4 cell/mL of live *Candida albicans* (Strain SC5314) in the presence and absence of varying concentrations of pilocarpine (1 mM, 5 mM, 25 mM) and incubated in 5% CO₂ at 37 °C for 4 and 24 h. Cells exposed to either pilocarpine alone or *Candida* alone served as positive controls and cells incubated with culture media only served as a negative control at each time point.

The bathing cell culture media (supernatant) was harvested in Eppendorf tubes and stored at 20 °C for later ELISA analysis and LDH cytotoxicity assays. The remaining adherent cells in each well were harvested by adding 350 uL of RLT lysing buffer containing 2-Mercaptoethanol (2-Hydroxyethylmercaptan; β -Mercaptoethanol, SIGMA) into each well followed by scraping. The lysate of each well was collected in an RNase-free Eppendorf and stored at -80 °C for later RNA extraction.

Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay

Quantification of IL-8 (CXCL8) and IL-6 levels in the supernatant samples were determined using commercially available Sandwich ELISA kits as per manufacturer instructions.

IL8 quantification was performed using PREPOTECH ELISA kit. Briefly, 96-well plates (Costar Assay Plate, Clear, Flat Bottom, High Binding Polystyrene Plate, USA) were coated with capture antibody and incubated over night at room temperature.

Three hundred microliter of blocking buffer (1% BSA in PBS) was added to each well and the plates were incubated for 2 h. The plates were washed 4 times with a wash buffer (0.05% Tween-20 in PBS). The standards were prepared by serially diluting a stock of 1000 pg/mL. One hundred microliter of each standard was added in duplicate into each well. One in ten dilution of supernatant samples in diluent (0.05% Tween-20, 0.1% BSA in PBS) was added to sample wells by adding 10 μ L of each sample supernatant and 90 μ L of diluent in duplicate, and the plates were incubated at room temperature for 2 h. Finally, the plates were treated with a detection antibody, washed, treated with streptavidin HRP, washed again followed by TMB (3,3',5,5'-*Tetramethylbenzidine*) plate development, and the colour change was read using FluoStar Omega® (BMG LABTECH, UK) microplate reader at 450 nm and 620 nm.

IL-6 quantification was performed using human uncoated Invitrogen ELISA kit. Briefly, 96-well plates (Costar Assay Plate, Clear, Flat Bottom, High Binding Polystyrene Plate, USA) were coated by capture antibody and incubated overnight at 4 °C.

The plates were washed five times between steps with PBS- 0.05% tween 20, blocked with 1X ELISA/ELISPOT and incubated for 1 h. One hundred microliter of prepared standards and 100 μ L of diluted samples (ten times dilution in 90 μ L of ELISA/ELISPOT diluent) were pipetted into each well and incubated at room temperature for 2 h. The plates were then treated with detection antibody, washed, treated with streptavidin HRF, washed again followed by TMB plate development in accordance to protocol, and the colour change was read at wavelength of 450nm and 570 nm (FluoStar Omega®, BMG LABTECH, UK). Data analysis was performed by BMG analysis software (BMG LABTECH).

RNA extraction, quantification, and cDNA synthesis

RNA extraction and purification

RNA extraction was conducted using the Qiagen RNeasy mini kit following the manufacturer instructions. Briefly, the frozen lysates containing Eppendorf tubes (samples + RLT lysing buffer containing 2-Mercaptoethanol) were retrieved from the freezer and allowed to defrost, then 350 μ L of 70% ethanol was added to each tube and mixed well by pipetting. The whole sample mixture (700 μ l) was transferred to an RNeasy Mini spin column (Qiagen), placed in a 2 mL collection tube (Qiagen), and centrifuged for 15 s at 13,000 RPM. The flow through at the bottom of each collection tube was discarded after the previous step and the subsequent steps below.

Three hundred and fifty microliters of buffer RW1 was added to each RNeasy column and centrifuged for 15 s at 13,000 RPM. A mixture of 10 μ l DNase and 70 μ l buffer RDD was then prepared, added directly to the RNeasy column membrane and incubated at 20-30 °C for 15 min. Buffer RW1 was added again and the tube centrifuged for 15 s at 13000 RPM. Buffer RPE was prepared and 500 μ l was pipetted into the RNeasy column which was subsequently centrifuged (15 s at 13,000 RPM), followed by addition of another 500 μ l of buffer RPE and again centrifuged for 2 min at 13,000 RPM. The RNase spin column was transferred to a new 1.5 mL collection tube and 50 μ l of RNase-free water was added to the spin column membrane and centrifuged for 1 min at 13,000 RPM to elute RNA.

The quantity and quality of the purified RNA of each sample were determined using Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific). RNA samples with a 260/280

ratio of 1.8-2.1 were deemed to be of high enough quality for subsequent PCR analysis. All samples were stored at -80°C for later analysis.

Reverse transcription

Reverse transcription was conducted using the High Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Reagents (Appliedbiosystems), following the manufacturer instructions. Briefly, 10 µL of RT⁺ and 10 µL of RT⁻ Master Mix were prepared for each sample as follows: [RT⁺ Master Mix (2 µL 10X RT Buffer, 0.8 µL 25X dNTP Mix (100 mM), 2 µL 10X RT Random Primers, 1 µL MultiscribeTM Reverse Transcriptase, 4.2 µL Nuclease-free H₂O), RT⁻ Master Mix (2 µL 10X RT Buffer, 0.8 µL 25X dNTP Mix (100 mM), 2 µL 10X RT Random Primers, 5.2 µL Nuclease-free H₂O)].

A Primus 96^{plus} thermal cycler was used to perform the reverse transcription reaction under the following conditions shown: [Step 1 (25 °C for 10 min), Step 2 (37 °C for 120 min), Step 3 (85 °C for 5 Sec), Step 4 (4 °C for ∞)]. Finally, the cDNA was immediately used for qPCR or stored at -20 °C.

Real-time quantitative PCR

The analysis of *IL-6* and *IL-8* mRNA expression was done using Power SYPER^{*} GREEN (Applied biosystem, Thermo Fisher Scientific) based qPCR and the expression was measured in relation to the house keeping gene glyceraldehyde-3-

phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH). The primers sequences used in this experiment are shown in Table 4.

A master mix containing 10 μ L Power SYPER* GREEN (Applied biosystem, Thermo Fisher Scientific), 7 μ L RNase free water, 1 μ L Forward primer, and 1 μ L Reverse primer (IL-6, IL-8, and GAPDH) were prepared as per the manufacturer instructions. one in 20 dilutions of cDNA samples were prepared by adding 19 μ L of master mix to each well of a 96-well real time plate (Thermo Fisher Scientific), followed by pipetting 1 μ L of each cDNA sample (RT⁺) into each well. RT- used as a control and H₂O only. The reaction was carried out on a Step-one real-time PCR machine (Thermo Fisher Scientific) under the following conditions: [Holding Stage (95.0 °C, 10 min), Cycling Stage (40 Cycles) ((95.0 °C, 15 Sec) and (60.0 °C, 1 min))].

Primer	Sequence of primer	Reference
IL-8 Forward	5'CAGAGACAGCAGAGCACACAA3'	(Li et al., 2007)
IL-8 Reverse	5'TTAGCACTCCTTGGCAAAAC3'	
IL-6 Forward	5'CAATCTGGATTCAATGAGGAGAC3'	(Girault et al., 2002)
IL-6 Reverse	5'CTCTGGCTTGTTCTTCACTACTC3'	
GAPDH Forward	5'CAAGGCTGAGAACGGGAAG3'	(McKimmie et al., 2008)
GAPDH Reverse	5'GGTGGTGAAGACGCCAGT3'	

Table 4: Primers used in this study. Primers and primer sequences were chosen in line with previous literature used in in all investigations.

Lactose Dehydrogenase Cytotoxicity Assay

Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) cytotoxicity Assay Kit (Thermo Scientific™ Pierce™) was used according to the manufacturer instructions to assess cytotoxicity. The assay was conducted by pipetting 20 µL of supernatant into six wells of a 96-well plate (Costar, Corning Incorporated, Flat-Bottomed Plate, NY, USA). Twenty microliters of LDH solution were pipetted into each well of the 96-well plate, which were wrapped with foil, and incubated for 30 min at room temperature. Finally, 20 µL of stop solution was pipetted into each well and the absorbance was measured using a microplate reader (FluoStar Omega, BMG LABTECH, UK) at an absorbance of 490 nm and 680 nm. The % cytotoxicity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ cytotoxicity} = \frac{(\text{Compound created LDH activity} - \text{Spontaneous LDH activity})}{(\text{Maximum LDH activity} - \text{Spontaneous LDH activity})} \times 100$$

Statistical analysis

GraphPad Prism 8 for windows (GraphPad Software, CA, USA) was used to perform the statistical analysis and to create the graphs for all microbiological and immunological assays. The real-time PCR data investigating change in *IL-6* and *IL-8* mRNA gene expression in cultured TR146 were calculated and presented as mean fold change in gene expression ($2^{-\text{ddct}}$) as previously described (Schmittgen and Livak, 2008). However, raw values (ddCT) were used for statistical analysis. The data from ELISA were calculated using the standards curve equation followed by dilution correction. Data from XXT metabolic reduction and crystal violet assays were blank corrected and presented as optical density (OD) absorbance values. Two-ways analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's were used to compare control samples

with each treatment condition. Man-Whitney non-parametric tests were used to compare between the total reduction of metabolic activity and biofilm biomass in LBF and HBF clinical isolates. A value of $P < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant.

Results

The effect of *C. albicans* and Pilocarpine on expression of Interleukin-6 and interleukin-8 by TR146 epithelial cells.

Figure 1A shows that 2×10^4 cell/mL live *C. albicans* significantly induced the release of IL-6 from TR146 cells after 24 h stimulation ($P < 0.01$). However, while pilocarpine alone did not induce a significant increase in levels of IL6 release by TR146 cells compared to media only controls at concentrations of 5 and 25 mM investigated after both 4h and 24 h stimulation, a concentration of 1 mM induced a significant increase in IL-6 release after 24 h stimulation only ($P < 0.05$). In addition, while there were no statistically significant differences in levels of IL-6 release between TR146 cells stimulated with *C. albicans* alone and cells stimulated with *C. albicans* and 1, 5 or 25 mM PHCL after 4h, the same concentrations resulted in statistically significant reduction after 24h ($P < 0.0001$). Interestingly, the reduction in levels of IL-6 release by *C. albicans* stimulated TR146 cells in the presence of PHCL seem to be following a dose-dependent pattern.

Figure 1B shows that 2×10^4 cell/mL Live *C. albicans* significantly induced *IL-6* mRNA expression by TR146 cells after both 4 h ($P < 0.01$) and 24 h ($P < 0.0001$) stimulation. However, pilocarpine alone did not induce a significant increase in *IL-6* mRNA expression by TR146 cells compared to media only controls at any of the concentrations investigated after both 4h and 24 h stimulation. Interestingly, when cells were stimulated for both 4 h ($P < 0.05$) and 24 h ($P < 0.01$) with *C. albicans* in the presence of 25 mM PHCL, there was a significant decrease in *IL-6* mRNA expression by TR146 cells compared to those stimulated with *C. albicans* alone.

Figure 1: The effect of *C. albicans* and Pilocarpine on expression of Interleukin-6 by TR146 epithelial cells. *C. albicans* induced the release of IL-6 by TR146 oral epithelial cells but PHCL inhibited *C. albicans* induced IL-6 release after 4 and 24 hours stimulation (A). This inhibition of IL-6 by PHCL was mediated at the transcriptional level (B). ELISA data (A) are expressed as mean pg/mL IL-6 release with standard deviation (SD) and derived from duplicate wells of 4 independent experiments (n=4). Statistical analysis of ELISA data was performed by log transferring the data followed by Two Way ANOVA with TUKEY post hoc multiple comparisons. The RT-PCR Data (B) are presented as fold induction change \pm standard deviation (SD) in *IL-6* mRNA expression in relation to unstimulated control ($2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$) and were derived from duplicate wells in 4 independent stimulations (n=4). Real time PCR statistical analysis was performed by Two Way ANOVA with TUKEY post hoc multiple comparisons. (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$; ***, $P < 0.001$; ****, $P < 0.0001$).

Figure 2A shows that 2×10^4 cells/mL live *C. albicans* significantly induced the release of IL-8 from TR146 cells after 24 h stimulation ($P < 0.05$). However, while pilocarpine alone did not induce a significant increase in levels of IL-8 release by TR146 cells compared to media only controls at concentrations of 5 and 25 mM investigated after both 4h and 24 h stimulation, a concentration of 1 mM induced a significant increase in IL-8 release after 24 h stimulation only ($P < 0.05$). However, while there were no statistically significant differences in levels of IL-8 release between TR146 cells stimulated with *C. albicans* alone and cells stimulated with *C. albicans* and 1 and 5 mM PHCL, the presence of 25 mM PHCL and *C. albicans* significantly reduced the release of IL-8 from TR146 cells compared to those stimulated with *C. albicans* alone.

Figure 2B shows that 2×10^4 cell/mL Live *C. albicans* significantly induced *IL-8* mRNA expression by TR146 cells after both 4 h ($P < 0.05$) and 24 h ($P < 0.0001$) stimulation. However, pilocarpine alone did not induce a significant increase in *IL-8* mRNA expression by TR146 cells compared to media only controls at any of the concentrations investigated after both 4h and 24 h stimulation. Nevertheless, while 1 and 5 mM PHCL concentrations resulted in an insignificant reduction of *IL-8* mRNA expression by TR146 compared to media only at both time intervals, a statistically significant reduction of TR146 *IL-8* gene expression was observed when *C. albicans* stimulation was performed in the presence of 25 mM PHCL after 24 hours.

Figure 2: The effect of *C. albicans* and Pilocarpine on expression of Interleukin-8 by TR146 epithelial cells. *C. albicans* induced the release of IL-8 by TR146 oral epithelial cells but PHCL inhibited *C. albicans* induced IL-8 release after 4 and 24 hours stimulation (A). This inhibition of IL-8 by PHCL was mediated at the transcriptional level (B). ELISA data (A) are expressed as mean pg/mL IL-8 release with standard deviation (SD) and derived from duplicate wells of 4 independent experiments (n= 4). Statistical analysis of ELISA data was performed by log transferring the data followed by Two Way ANOVA with TUKEY post hoc multiple comparisons. The RT-PCR Data (B) are presented as fold induction change \pm standard deviation (SD) in *IL-8* mRNA expression in relation to unstimulated control ($2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$) and were derived from duplicate wells in 4 independent stimulations (n=4). Real time PCR statistical analysis was performed by Two Way ANOVA with TUKEY post hoc multiple comparisons. (*, P<0.05; **, P<0.01; ***, P<0.001; ****, P<0.0001).

To ensure any of the effects observed in Figures 1 and 2 were not due to cytotoxic effects of pilocarpine or *C. albicans*, Lactate Dehydrogenase assay was performed. Figure 3 shows that neither Pilocarpine at the concentrations used in this study or *C. albicans* had a significant effect on TR146 viability.

Figure 3: PHCL and live *C. albicans* have no significant cytotoxic effects on TR146 cell viability under the conditions used in this study. TR146 epithelial cells were cultured in a 24-well plate in the presence of *C. albicans* (2×10^4 cells/mL) +/- PHCL (1, 5 and 25 mM) as previously described and the bathing supernatant harvested after 4 and 24 h. The Lactate Dehydrogenase Assay (LDH) was used to determine cytotoxicity. The data is presented as percentage cytotoxicity calculated from corrected row OD₄₉₀ values derived from triplicate wells in four independent occasions (n=4), using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ cytotoxicity} = \frac{(\text{Compound created LDH activity} - \text{Spontaneous LDH activity})}{(\text{Maximum LDH activity} - \text{Spontaneous LDH activity})} \times 100 .$$

The effect of Pilocarpine hydrochloride on biofilm forming ability of clinical *C. albicans* isolates.

C. albicans exhibits heterogeneity in biofilm forming ability (Ramage et al., 2002b) and previously pilocarpine has been shown to inhibit biofilm formation by laboratory strain of *C. albicans* SC3514 (Nile et al., 2019). The effect of PHCL on biofilm formation by clinical *Candida* isolates, classified as low (LBF) or high (HBF) biofilm formers in previous studies (Coco et al., 2008), (O'Donnell et al., 2017), was therefore investigated.

Overall, 24 hours treatment with 25 mM PHCL resulted in a significant biofilm biomass reduction by both LBF and HBF isolates (P-value<0.0001), (Figure 4A and C). At a strain specific level, almost all strains investigated, whether LBF or HBF isolates, exhibited a significant reduction in biofilm formation after treatment with 25 mM PHCL, (Figure 4B and D). This included 7 HBF [P-value: (BC 020, GSK 004, GSK 025, GSK 061, GSK 090) <0.0001; (GSK 010) <0.01; (GSK 093) <0.05)] and 6 LBF isolates [P-value: (BC 023, BC 037, GSK 031, GSK 053, GSK 065, GSK 123) <0.0001], (Figure 4B and D). Indeed only the following strains exhibited no significant response in biofilm biomass formation when exposed to PHCL; [LBF (BC 038, BC 039, BC 044, GSK 072, GSK 113); HBF (BC 117, BC 136, BC 145, BC 146)].

Figure 4: PHCL reduced biofilm formation in LBF and HBF clinical *Candida* isolates. Biofilm biomass was assessed using crystal violet assay after culturing each *Candida* isolate at a cell density of 1×10^6 cell/mL for 24 h in RPMI \pm 25 mM PHCL. Panels A and C compare the overall effect of RPMI \pm 25 mM PHCL on biofilm biomass after 24 h on Low (LBF) or high (HBF) biofilm-forming isolates, respectively. Data in panels B and D show the effect of RPMI \pm 25 mM PHCL on the biofilm biomass at a strain specific level. Data in panels A and C were expressed as mean OD₅₇₀ values with standard deviation of total LBF or HBF isolates derived from quadruplicate wells per isolate of three independent experiments (n= 3). Statistical analysis for panels A and C were performed using non-parametric Man Whitney test. Data in panels B and D were expressed as mean OD₅₇₀ values, and each symbol represents mean values with a standard deviation (SD) of quadruplicate wells of three independent experiments (n=3). Statistical analysis in panels B and C was performed using Two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test. Significance level indicated by airstrikes as follows: (*, P<0.05; **, P<0.01; ***, P<0.001; ****, P<0.0001).

Previously PHCL induced inhibition of *C. albicans* biofilm formation has been shown to coincide with a reduction in metabolic output not attributable to cytotoxicity (Nile et al., 2019).

Overall, 24 hours treatment with 25 mM PHCL resulted in a statistically significant reduction of the metabolic activity of HBF clinical *C. albicans* isolates compared to the control ($P > 0.0001$), while the same concentration did not produce a significant reduction in metabolic activity in LBF clinical *C. albicans* isolates, (Figure 5A and C). At a strain specific level, three HBF isolates had a significant reduction in metabolic activity after treatment with 25 mM PHCL [P-value: (GSK 004, GSK 010) < 0.0001 , (GSK 061) < 0.05], and a single LBF isolate had a significant metabolic reduction [P-value (GSK 123) = 0.0001], (Figure 5B and D). Indeed the following strains exhibited no significant reduction in metabolic output when exposed to PHCL; [LBF (BC 023, BC 037, BC 038, BC 039, BC 044, GSK 031, GSK 053, GSK 065, GSK 072, GSK 113); HBF (BC 020, BC 117, BC 136, BC 145, BC 146, GSK 025, GSK 090, GSK 093)].

Figure 5: PHCL reduced metabolic activity in HBF Clinical *Candida* isolates. Biofilm metabolic activity was assessed by XTT assay after culturing each *Candida* isolate at a cell density of 1×10^6 cells/mL for 24h in RPMI \pm 25 mM PHCL. Panels A and C compare the overall effect of RPMI \pm 25 mM PHCL on metabolic activity after 24 h on Low (LBF) or high (HBF) biofilm-forming isolates, respectively. Data in panels B and D show the effect of RPMI \pm 25 mM PHCL on the metabolic output at a strain specific level. Data in panels A and C were expressed as mean OD₅₇₀ values with standard deviation of total LBF or HBF isolates derived from quadruplicate wells per isolate of three independent experiments (n= 3). Statistical analysis for panels A and C were performed using non-parametric Man Whitney test. Data in panels B and D were expressed as mean OD₅₇₀ values, and each symbol represents mean values with a standard deviation (SD) of quadruplicate wells of three independent experiments (n=3). Statistical analysis in panels B and C was performed using Two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test. Significance level indicated by airstrikes as follows: (*, P<0.05; **, P<0.01; ***, P<0.001; ****, P<0.0001).

Discussion

Pilocarpine hydrochloride (PHCL) is used clinically for the management of conditions defined by loss or gain of cholinergic functions (Tata et al., 2014). The expression of cholinergic receptors by human cells, fungi, bacteria and plants, in addition to their multiple functions, make these receptors a promising target for drugs to treat non-neurological infectious pathologies. Data from a previous study using *Galleria mellonella* infection model showed that PHCL, a general muscarinic receptor agonist, can regulate *C. albicans* filamentation and biofilm formation whilst modulating the host immune response and protecting against mortality (Nile et al., 2019).

The first part of this study looked for the host modulatory effect of PHCL on *C. albicans* infected TR146 epithelial cell model. The infection of human epithelial cells by *C. albicans* stimulates the release of different cytokines by these cells to orchestrate the immune defense and attract neutrophils to the infection site. Research has suggested that the release of IL-8 and IL-6 from *Candida*-infected oral keratinocytes, induce neutrophils recruitment and activation (Feller et al., 2014). In addition, a study using a mouse model found that IL-6 is an important cytokine that enhances the candidal activity of neutrophils (Van Enkevort et al., 1999). However, while other proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 α and TNF have been shown as being beneficial for the defense against *C. albicans*, research on IL-6 knock-out mice has found that IL-6 has more immune protective activities on its own that cannot be compensated by other cytokines (Van Enkevort et al., 1999), (Dalrymple et al., 1995). Moreover, the IL-6 signaling pathway has been suggested to be involved in the activation of IL-8 production through nuclear factor IL-6 (NF-IL-6) in *C. albicans*-infected gingival epithelial cells (Tsushima et al., 2011). NF-IL-6 has been shown to

play an important role in the regulation of genes responsible for immune and inflammatory responses (Tsushima et al., 2011). The data of this paper confirms the results of previous studies as both IL-6 and IL-8 are expressed by TR146 cells in response to *C. albicans* infection.

Additionally, the data shows that PHCL-treated TR146 epithelial cells demonstrated a significant increase in IL-8 and IL-6 at the protein level when exposed to a concentration of 1 mM. However, this increased expression was not observed using higher concentrations of 5 mM and 25 mM PHCL. Nevertheless, PHCL at all concentrations induced a non-significant increase in *IL6* and *IL8* mRNA gene expression by TR146 compared to untreated control.

While there is a variation in protein expression pattern between the two assays in non-infected PHCL-treated epithelial cells, several reasons have been suggested by research for lack of correlation between mRNA and protein abundance (Greenbaum et al., 2003). One of these reasons is simply due to the fact that ELISA provides a quick summary of overall protein release after reaction compared to real-time PCR which detects the actual gene of interest at real-time (Sue et al., 2014). Also, based on the presence of slightly higher *IL-6* and *IL-8* gene expression after 4h compared to 24 h in non-infected PHCL-treated epithelial cells at a concentration of 1 mM and 5 mM, we hypothesize that the early cellular response to PHCL may differ than late response.

As well as being a general muscarinic receptor (mAChR) agonist, pharmacological research has suggested that PHCL's major effect has predominance for the M1 mAChR subtype; and to a lesser extent M3 mAChR in mammals (Figuroa et al., 2009). Data from human studies have shown that different muscarinic receptor subtypes could have opposing functions (Zhang et al., 2006), (Zhang et al., 2007),

(Profita et al., 2008), (Kistemaker et al., 2013). For instance, several studies have highlighted the importance of both M1 and M2 mAChsR in the modulation of the cellular pattern of inflammation in human cells, (Kistemaker et al., 2013), (Profita et al., 2008). Furthermore, blocking the M3 mAChR has been shown to reduce expression of *IL-8* and *IL-6* during an inflammatory response (Kistemaker et al., 2013), (Profita et al., 2008). A study on mice demonstrated that the M3 mAChR is involved in CD4 T-cell activation and cytokine production in two different murine infection models (Darby et al., 2015). However, the blocking of M1 and M2 has been shown to aggravate the inflammatory response (Kistemaker et al., 2013). The results of these studies suggest that M1 and M2 rather than M3 mAChR subtypes could be responsible for the immune modulatory-response targeted by PHCL.

On the other hand, research has suggested that PHCL has a receptor affinity (RA_i) of 0.49, 0.015, 0.21, and 0.01 across M1 to M4 mAChsR, respectively (Figuroa et al., 2009). Studies have shown that a lower drug concentration is required for a full receptor saturation in receptors with high affinity for a certain drug, and vice versa (Lambert, 2004), (Salahudeen and Nishtala, 2017), (Salahudeen and Nishtala, 2017). The slight dose-dependent increase in *IL-6* and *IL-8* mRNA expression by non-infected TR146 from a concentration of 1mM to 25mM after 24 h, may have been resulted from receptor uptake affinity for M1 mAChR at low concentration compared to M3 mAChR at high concentration. Thus, we could hypothesize that M1 mAChR is important for modulating inflammation.

In contrast, a dose-dependent inhibition in both *IL-6* and *IL-8* protein expression occurred in TR146 cells stimulated with *C. albicans* and PHCL after treatment compared to those stimulated with *C. albicans* alone. However, this inhibition was only significant at a concentration of 25 mM PHCL. The dual effect of PHCL by

activating mAChsR expression on both cells and *C. albicans* is suggested behind the improved immune response, by overriding the cellular effects of *Candida*, and reducing biofilm formation. It is interesting how both ELISA and qPCR were correlated in this part of the study, which is not fully understood. However, factors such as cellular consumption of cytokines (Amsen et al., 2009) and the synergistic effect of PHCL on both *C. albicans* and cells might have led to this correlation.

The second part of this study investigated the effect of PHCL on 22 clinical *C. albicans* isolates, which had previously been characterized as low (LBF) and high (HBF) biofilm-formers. The biofilm forming ability of *C. albicans* has been suggested to enhance their virulence by increasing their resistance to antimicrobial therapy, with higher drug concentrations are required to eliminate biofilms compared to free-floating planktonic cells (Ramage et al., 2012). In addition, studies have shown a positive correlation between poor treatment outcome and biofilm architecture, which is linked to *C. albicans* filamentation (Ramage et al., 2002a), (Tumbarello et al., 2012). Despite the role of hyphae in biofilm formation, previous research on clinical isolates has shown variability in their biofilm forming capabilities (Ramage et al., 2011). Moreover, a significant correlation has been found between *C. albicans* biofilm formation and mortality due to candidemia (Ramage et al., 2011). Therefore, molecules that can neutralize fungal biofilms by controlling filamentation represents an attractive therapeutic option for treatment of life-threatening infectious fungal conditions.

Studies have suggested that PHCL has no fungicidal abilities but acts through a yet uncharacterized *C. albicans* G-coupled receptor, to regulate filamentation (Rajendran et al., 2015a), (Nile et al., 2019). These receptors are similar in phenotype to human muscarinic receptors. Therefore, different receptors in *Candida* could be responsible

for different function (filamentation, virulence and biofilm formation). However, further research is required to confirm this hypothesis. Nevertheless, research has shown that PHCL can reduce the cell surface hydrophobicity of *Candida* species (Nile et al., 2019). This reduction has been suggested to be a predictor of the cell biofilm forming potential of *C. albicans* (Mayer et al., 2013). In addition, a study has found that a correlation could exist between cell surface hydrophobicity and metabolic activity in *C. albicans* and *C. tropicalis* (Silva-Dias et al., 2015). As the hydrophobicity of *C. albicans* increases both biofilms forming potential and metabolic activity increases. In this study, PHCL was found to significantly reduce biofilm formation in most HBF and LBF *Candida* isolates, Figure 4A and C. However, a larger sample size might be required to confirm the drug response heterogeneity between the isolates.

Since M1 and M3 muscarinic receptor subtypes utilize calcium as a secondary messenger to control the morphogenesis of *C. albicans* (Qin et al., 2011), (Holmes et al., 1991), we suggest that pilocarpine may have led to more calcium uptake especially in HBF isolates, which resulted in a slightly more effective biofilm biomass reduction in HBF compared to LBF isolates that have already reduced metabolic activity. Also, our data here show a significant overall reduction in the metabolic activity of HBF clinical isolates after treatment with 25 mM PHCL for 24h compared to control, but the same PHCL concentration resulted in an insignificant reduction in metabolic activity in LBF clinical isolates, Figure 5. Therefore, this confirms the existing evidence of correlation between biofilm formation ability and metabolic activity (Jin et al., 2003), (Li et al., 2003), (Melo et al., 2011).

This study has several limitations, such as the small sample size, the use of non-selective muscarinic receptor agonist and the limited knowledge about the muscarinic receptors responsible for filamentation in *C. albicans*. Further studies should

concentrate on using selective muscarinic receptor agonists to determine the exact function of each receptor in human cells. Also, it might be necessary to characterize the receptors that are responsible for controlling filamentation in *C. albicans*. Finally, this *in vitro* model may not be able to reflect the exact pathophysiology of *C. albicans* infection in human cells and the response to treatment, therefore a more representative 3D infection model or an *in vivo* approach is recommended.

In conclusion, we suggest that PHCL has multiple functions due to its ability to act on more than one muscarinic receptor presented in both *C. albicans* and epithelial cells. Accordingly, the effect of PHCL on *C. albicans* infected TR146 was more robust due to its anti-biofilm, anti-metabolic, anti-cell surface adhesion roles on *C. albicans* on one hand and host modulatory effect on TR146 epithelial cells on the other hand. However, determining the exact function of each muscarinic receptor in both *C. albicans* and human epithelial cells could enable us to develop a receptor-specific direct or adjunctive therapeutic strategy to treat and prevent life-threatening fungal infections.

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